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Tracce Project – ICTs in Support of
Monza's Plan for the Elimination of
Architectural Barriers

Participatory, GIS-Based and
AI-Assisted Approach to
Accessibility for People with
Reduced Mobility

Inclusive Mobility, Research

Tracce Project: ICTs in Support of Monza's Plan for the Elimination of Architectural Barriers

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Abstract

This paper presents the Tracce project, a research project carried out by Fondazione Transform Transport ETS in collaboration with the Municipality of Monza and Monza Mobilità S.r.l. The main objective of the project was to gain a comprehensive understanding of the level of accessibility and mobility needs of people with reduced mobility in the city of Monza, by adopting an integrated methodological approach combining participatory co-design, GIS-based spatial analysis, AI-powered detection of accessibility barriers, and digital tool development. The methodology was structured in three phases: identification of priority barriers through literature review, participatory workshops, and an online survey; GIS Mapping of elements such as pedestrian network, accessibility attributes based on the previously identified barriers. the development of digital tools, including an interactive WebGIS platform and Tracce.app, a web application providing multi-criteria accessible routing and a crowdsourced barrier-reporting function. The paper discusses how the integration of participatory methods, geospatial data, AI, and digital tools can transform a static planning instrument, such as the Plan for the Elimination of Architectural Barriers (PEBA), into a dynamic, adaptive monitoring process.

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Urban Accessibility, People with Reduced Mobility, Participatory Process, User-based Routing.

1. Introduction

Urban accessibility for people with reduced mobility (PRM), including wheelchair users, elderly individuals, parents with strollers, and people with temporary or permanent physical limitations, remains one of the most persistent challenges in contemporary city planning. Physical barriers in the public realm not only limit independent movement but also restrict social participation and quality of life, affecting a significant and growing share of the urban population. At policy level, the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (United Nations, 2006) establishes Design for All as a legal obligation for signatory states, while the European Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021–2030 (European Commission, 2021) sets the target of making all public buildings and transport infrastructure accessible by 2030.

In this context, the Plan for the Elimination of Architectural Barriers (Piano di Eliminazione delle Barriere Architettoniche - PEBA) represents the primary statutory instrument through which Italian municipalities are required to systematically identify, prioritize, and remove physical barriers from the public realm. Developed in

accordance with the 2023 Regional Guidelines of Regione Lombardia, Monza's PEBA adopts a multidisciplinary approach that integrates sustainable mobility, social inclusion, participatory design, and digital technologies. Rather than limiting its scope to the removal of isolated physical obstacles, the PEBA of Monza is conceived as a strategic, city-wide instrument for improving the overall quality of urban life for all residents.

It is within this framework that the Tracce project ("Tracce - ICT Technologies in Support of Monza's Plan for the Elimination of Architectural Barriers") was designed and implemented. Funded by Monza Mobilità S.r.l. and carried out by Fondazione Transform Transport ETS in collaboration with the Municipality of Monza (Mobility and Infrastructure Assessorate; Participation, Housing Policy, Youth, and Equal Opportunities Assessorate), the project ran from February 2025 to June 2026. Its core objective was to analyze urban mobility in Monza by placing PRM user experience at the center of the research process, in alignment with the UX Mobility methodology developed by Systematica and Transform Transport (2025).

The project set out to understand the needs and expectations of PRM through direct engagement, while simultaneously building a quantitative spatial knowledge base through geolocated GIS mapping. These two strands, qualitative and quantitative, were designed to complement and reinforce each other, feeding into the development of a user-based routing system capable of generating accessible itineraries tailored to individual user needs. Beyond the tool itself, the project aimed to place actionable data and metrics in the hands of decision-makers and urban planners, and to contribute substantively to the drafting of the PEBA, ultimately in service of a broader vision of Monza as an inclusive, accessible city for all its residents.

It opens by framing the research through a review of the scientific literature and an analysis of existing international case studies and digital tools for inclusive mobility. The methodological core then follows the chronological arc of the project: from the participatory workshop and survey that identified priority barriers, through the GIS mapping of the pedestrian network and the AI-assisted detection of architectural barriers, to the co-design process and technical development of the web application. The paper then presents the results produced by these activities: the interactive WebGIS platform and the web application Tracce.app, including an analysis of its first months of use. It closes with conclusions and directions for future research and development.

1.1 Literature Review

The concept of urban accessibility is inherently multidimensional, encompassing spatial, social, and temporal dimensions of the built environment. The foundational framework proposed by Geurs and van Wee (2004) distinguishes four components of accessibility: land use (the spatial distribution of activities), transport (the characteristics of mobility networks), time (the temporal availability of individuals), and individual factors (personal capabilities and resources). It should be noted that this framework addresses accessibility in a general sense, related to the opportunity of reaching activities and services, rather than accessibility in the sense more specifically associated with disability and reduced mobility, as in PRM. The latter notion, which is the focus of the Tracce project, can nonetheless be situated within Geurs and van Wee's taxonomy: infrastructure-related barriers fall primarily within the *transport* component, while individual limitations, such as motor or cognitive impairments, are more directly attributable to the *individual factors* component.

Physical accessibility, understood as the absence of barriers in the built environment that would otherwise impede the autonomous movement of people with motor, sensory, or cognitive impairments, has been the object of growing methodological attention. The treatment of disability in urban planning has gained increasing attention since the early 2000s, in parallel with the consolidation of the social model of disability (Oliver, 1990), which shifts the analytical focus from individual impairments to environmental and social barriers.

The psychological and subjective dimensions of accessibility have also received growing attention. Mora et al. (2017) show that anticipatory anxiety generated by uncertainty about route conditions constitutes a barrier to mobility in its own right, independently of actual physical conditions. Sze and Christensen (2017) demonstrate that the perception of exclusion from public transport negatively affects the social participation of people with disabilities.

These findings directly informed the design of the Tracce web application, which was conceived not only to calculate accessible routes but also to provide users with transparent information about route characteristics, thereby reducing uncertainty and increasing confidence in autonomous urban navigation. The integration of GIS

technologies and open geospatial data has significantly advanced this area, enabling systematic forms of urban assessment beyond traditional field surveys. Hara et al. (2014) demonstrated that computer vision techniques applied to Google Street View images can automatically detect curb ramps with high accuracy, opening the way for systematic, cost-effective urban mapping at scale, an approach experimented in the present project. The importance of active user participation in the co-design of digital accessibility tools is equally well established: Wheeler et al. (2020) demonstrate that accessible wayfinding systems developed without the direct involvement of end users tend to underestimate the complexity and variability of real-world needs. Key normative references include the Eurocities City Guidelines (Eurocities, 2019), the UK Department for Transport's Accessible Public Realm (DfT, 2020) and Inclusive Mobility (DfT, 2021), and the Walk21 Foundation framework. The latter categorizes the pedestrian experience into 11 thematic categories and 33 specific indicators and has been adopted as a methodological reference for indicator selection in this study.

1.2 Existing Case Studies

The European Access City Award, promoted by the European Commission since 2010, provides a significant comparative sample of approaches to urban accessibility across European contexts, evaluating progress in four domains: (i) built environment and public spaces; (ii) transport and related infrastructure; (iii) information and communication; (iv) and public services and facilities. Cities recognized in recent years illustrate distinct strategic orientations. In 2021, Breda was distinguished for a systemic approach integrating universal design into all new infrastructure interventions, complemented by a participatory monitoring system involving disability associations. Whereas in 2017, Chester developed an accessibility audit model based on evaluative walks conducted jointly by municipal technicians and users with diverse disability types, a methodological approach directly comparable to the participatory mapping activity implemented in the Tracce project. In 2016, Milan received recognition for the “Milano Accessibile” mobile application and investments in barrier removal at metro stations, while Grenoble stands out for the integration of pedestrian accessibility with the public transport system and the publication of open-format accessibility maps. Rotterdam has implemented a system for planning accessible itineraries integrated into the municipal mobility platform, with continuous data updates through citizen contributions. Collectively, these examples reveal a common tendency: the most advanced cities on accessibility combine scheduled infrastructure interventions with digital monitoring and participation tools, in a continuous cycle of detection, action, and verification, a model that directly informed the design of the Tracce project.

A comparative analysis of existing digital applications for inclusive mobility was also conducted. The review highlights that most existing solutions concentrate on two primary functions: participatory barrier mapping (e.g., Wheelmap, Via Libera, WeGlad etc.) and assisted navigation for specific sensory disabilities (e.g., NaviLens, NaviBlind, Waymap etc.). Applications oriented toward accessible pedestrian routing, planning itineraries that account for infrastructure characteristics in a structured and customizable manner, remain relatively rare and tend to offer standardized user profiles with limited personalization. The benchmarking exercise confirmed a recurring gap: the scarcity of open, standardized data on pedestrian accessibility at urban scale. OpenStreetMap constitutes the primary data source for most reviewed applications, but completeness and accuracy of accessibility attributes vary considerably across cities and neighborhoods. The systematic mapping conducted within the Tracce project represents an original contribution to filling this gap for the territory of Monza.

2. Methodology

The methodology of the Tracce project unfolded chronologically across three interrelated phases, each building upon the outputs of the previous one. The first phase focused on identifying priority barriers through participatory methods and a large-scale survey. The second phase involved the construction of a detailed GIS database including the pedestrian network of Monza and the mapping of urban architectural barriers, and the testing of AI-assisted image detection. The third phase combined further co-design activities with the technical development and public launch of the digital tools, WebGIS platform and web application. This section is

structured to outline the methods behind each phase and briefly describe outline some of the results of the initial activities, with the idea of painting a comprehensive picture of the whole project.

2.1 Identifying Priority Barriers

The first phase of the project, initiated in February 2025, combined a systematic indicator selection process with two complementary participatory data collection activities: a co-design workshop and an online survey. The selection of accessibility indicators was grounded in the Walk21 Foundation framework, which organizes the pedestrian experience into 11 thematic categories and 33 specific indicators. These indicators were evaluated for their relevance to the Monza context through the first participatory workshop, resulting in a three-tier classification: (i) essential elements (those critical for guaranteeing access and safety for PRM); (ii) relevant elements (factors limiting mobility experience without constituting absolute architectural barriers); (iii) and non-relevant elements (considered marginal within the project scope).

The first participatory workshop was held on March 21st 2025 at the Centro Civico di San Fruttuoso in Monza, with 18 volunteer participants and representatives of the Municipality of Monza. Participants were recruited through local disability organizations and district advisory councils. In the first part of the workshop, the participants were divided in three groups and engaged in a structured discussion supported by thematic canvas sheets, identifying locations in Monza associated with particularly positive or problematic mobility experiences, with attention to both physical elements and an emotional dimension that surfaced recurrent feelings of anxiety, frustration, and exclusion. In the second plenary part of the workshop, results were synthesized to identify the factors considered most relevant to urban accessibility. Participants systematically distinguished between architectural barriers, elements that structurally prevent autonomous movement, and less severe constraints that reduce usability of public spaces. Among the primary barriers identified were narrow or uneven sidewalks, excessive slopes, fixed and mobile obstacles (such as poles or illegally parked vehicles), crossings without auditory signals, absent or inadequate ramps, insufficient lighting, and excessive vehicle speed. Positive elements included well-maintained pedestrian areas, raised level pedestrian crossings, 30 km/h zones, uniform pavement surfaces, and clear visual reference points.

Figure 1 Results of the first co-design workshop (negative elements in red, positive elements in blue, and mixed elements in purple).

Complementary to the workshop, an online survey was distributed between March and August 2025 to quantitatively characterize mobility conditions and barrier perceptions among PRM users and their caregivers across Monza. The questionnaire was structured in six sections covering demographics, active mobility patterns, physical characteristics of pedestrian routes, recurring obstacles, complementary accessibility indicators, and open observations. It collected 220 responses from a predominantly adult sample (over 55% aged above 45 years, 56.8% female). Approximately 12% of respondents reported having a disability, with 9% belonging specifically to the group of people with mobility impairment. Of the total number of participants, 66% of respondents (132 out of 220) reported having encountered significant difficulties during active travel in Monza's public space. This figure includes caregivers, family members, and individuals who had experienced indirect or temporary mobility difficulties. Over 70% indicated a minimum sidewalk width of 1.2 meters as a prerequisite for accessibility, and more than 60% identified cobblestone and gravel surfaces as strongly problematic. Among the most frequently reported obstacles were illegally parked vehicles and scooters, waste and bins on public pathways, tree roots, and urban furniture such as poles and signage. These findings confirmed the need for mapping tools capable of capturing not only static accessibility conditions but also dynamic and temporary barriers, and they directly informed both the GIS attribute selection and the design of the application's reporting function.

2.2 GIS Mapping

The data collection and GIS mapping phase was initiated in April 2025 and extended through May 2025. Its objective was to build a comprehensive spatial knowledge base on the factors influencing PRM mobility in Monza, integrating three complementary source categories: open-access data (OpenStreetMap; SIT Geoportal);

proprietary data provided by Monza Mobilità and the Municipality; and data produced directly by Transform Transport through manual mapping and spatial analyses. The five datasets incorporated into the pedestrian graph are summarized in *Table 1*.

Indicator	Detail	Data Source	Year
Pedestrian paths	Sidewalk width	Transform Transport (field survey + GIS)	2025
Pedestrian paths	Longitudinal slope	DBGT / Digital Terrain Model (DTM)	2025
Crossings	Pedestrian crossings (with/without ramps)	Transform Transport (OSM + Municipality)	2025
Urban furniture	Street lighting density	Municipality of Monza	2024
Traffic	Road accidents (2022–2024)	Monza Mobilità S.r.l.	2022–2023–2024

Table 1 Geospatial datasets collected and incorporated into the pedestrian graph.

Alongside conventional data collection, an experimental pipeline was developed and tested to evaluate the potential of Artificial Intelligence for the automated detection of architectural barriers at urban scale. The pipeline focused on curb ramp detection at pedestrian crossings, given their critical importance for wheelchair accessibility and the practical infeasibility of systematic manual surveying across the entire municipality. A reference dataset was manually compiled within a sample area of Monza: 538 pedestrian crossings were identified and geolocated, recording for each the presence or absence of ramps on both sides. Street View imagery (SVI) was then automatically collected via the Google Maps API, extracting two images per crossing oriented toward the starting point and the ending point of the crossing. Two categories of models were evaluated: pre-trained object detection models (YOLOv8, DeepLabv3, Roboflow) (Chen et al., 2018; Nelson & Dwyer, 2020; Vijayakumar & Vairavasundaram, 2024), whose performance on Monza imagery proved limited due to domain mismatch; and multimodal large language models (LLMs), including LLaVA-NeXT (Liu et al., 2024), ChatGPT (Johnson et al., 2023), and Google Gemini 2.0/2.5 (Team et al, 2023), which jointly process images and text. Gemini demonstrated the highest accuracy, and a central methodological finding was the critical role of prompt design: small textual variations produced significant differences in detection rates. With the temperature parameter set to its minimum value for deterministic outputs, model performance evaluated on 251 images yielded accuracy ranged from 0.58 and 0.72 and F1-score up to 83%. These results confirm the potential of AI-assisted mapping while highlighting current limitations linked to image quality, dataset imbalance, and model sensitivity to input parameters.

Figure 2 Illustration of the Analysis Objective on Google Street View images.

The systematic mapping of Monza's pedestrian network was carried out starting in May 2025. To ensure a structured approach, the entire municipal territory was divided into nine regular 2 × 2 km quadrants. The pedestrian graph was built starting from OSM data, selecting edges classified as pedestrian streets, footways, steps, and paths, further disaggregating footways into sidewalks, crossings, and traffic islands. Since OSM data presented significant gaps, with many sidewalk segments missing and pedestrian crossings strongly underrepresented, an extensive refinement process was undertaken in QGIS and ArcGIS, combining the OSM Sidewalkreator plugin (which automatically generates sidewalk geometries from road center lines using hierarchically differentiated buffers) with extensive manual editing. Within Monza's historic center and Limited Traffic Zone (ZTL), all streets were treated as fully walkable regardless of formal classification, in order to realistically represent pedestrian usage conditions. An isometric analysis from Piazza Duomo using a 6,500-metre threshold confirmed that the accessible graph achieved 91.67% network connectivity, with approximately 8.33% of the pedestrian network remaining disconnected, primarily in peripheral residential areas around Via Alserio, in Sant'Alessandro, and in the Sant'Albino district. These areas were subsequently reconnected by introducing road center lines for streets without formal pedestrian infrastructure, ensuring full territorial coverage while maintaining a semantic distinction between actual accessible segments and topological completion connectors.

Once the graph structure was finalized, each edge was enriched with the selected accessibility indicators. Sidewalk width was derived from manual digitization on Google Earth satellite imagery, assigning to each segment its minimum measurable width to represent the most restrictive accessibility condition; a spatial inference procedure using 2-metre buffer intersections with adjacent edges was applied to fill remaining gaps. Longitudinal slope was derived from a TIN interpolation of ground-level elevation points from the DBGT dataset of Regione Lombardia, with quality-control corrections applied to subways, railway infrastructures, and viaducts. Pedestrian crossing accessibility was encoded using a three-level 'step' attribute: step = 0 (fully accessible, ramps on both sides), step = 1 (partial barrier, ramp missing on one side), and step = 2 (full barrier, ramps absent on both sides). Street lighting density was computed from a municipal point-layer dataset of lighting poles, using 15-metre road buffers to calculate the number of poles per linear meter per graph edge. Road accident data covering 2022–2023–2024 were provided by Monza Mobilità as geolocated point events and associated to graph edges using 20-metre buffers.

2.3 Development of the Web Application

The development of the Tracce web application ran in parallel with the mapping phase and was structured through two additional participatory workshops that defined and validated the application's features at successive stages of maturity. The second co-design workshop was held on the 10th of July 2025 at Villa Fossati Lamperti, Monza, with 13 volunteer participants divided into three groups. The session moved from a high-level

brainstorming phase on hypothetical digital platform functionalities to progressively more detailed discussion of the specific features that would shape Tracce.app. All groups emphasized the need for comprehensive mapping of mobility-critical urban elements differentiated by disability type, and unanimously identified customization of the app as essential: users should be able to configure individual preferences, save habitual routes, and adapt the interface to their specific needs and profile. A shared reporting system was proposed, with moderation mechanisms and the categorization of barriers to synthesize user comments. Participants also highlighted that travel time is not an absolute criterion but is strictly linked to route quality and safety, suggesting that the application should offer multiple routing options for informed user choice.

Figure 3 Second participatory workshop, with the objective of understanding requested webapp functionalities.

Building on these inputs, the routing engine of Tracce.app was developed between March and August 2025, based on the enriched pedestrian graph. Route calculation employs a multi-criteria Dijkstra algorithm, always returning two simultaneous solutions: a fastest path, shortest path by metric distance, and an accessible path, parametric cost function incorporating accessibility attributes. User-defined parameters are translated into hard constraints, which remove non-compliant segments from the graph prior to calculation, and soft cost weights, which influence the cost function without excluding segments. Hard constraints include requiring ramps at crossings, avoiding steps, and enforcing minimum sidewalk width. Soft cost weights cover road safety and accident density, lighting quality preference, and slope, favoring flatter routes. To reduce initial configuration complexity, four pre-configured user profiles are available (i.e., *wheelchair user*, *person with motor disability*, *parent with stroller*, and *other*), each initializing the routing engine with parameter values consistent with the profile's typical needs. The software architecture of Tracce.app is based on JavaScript with a responsive, cross-platform frontend hosted on DigitalOcean App Platform with CDN distribution, and a backend running a PostgreSQL database extended with pgRouting for routing logic and data persistence. All data processing complies with GDPR (EU, 2016/679) requirements, including HTTPS encryption, rate limiting, and data minimization.

The testing of the webapp was held during the third co-design workshop was held on the 19th of November 2025 at the Centro Civico San Carlo–San Giuseppe, Monza, with approximately 20 volunteer participants. The session combined an indoor phase, with participants testing the application at tables within the civic center, and an outdoor participatory mapping exercise in the surrounding neighborhood: a 500-metre guided walk along a route

comparing an accessible slightly longer path with a shorter alternative interrupted by a sidewalk segment below the minimum width threshold. Participant feedback identified several improvement priorities: (i) improved chromatic contrast and larger icons on the interface, (particularly for visually impaired users); (ii) the ability to save preferred routes and access Points of Interest with accessibility information; (iii) introduction of a surface quality category and dynamic obstacles (e.g., *illegal parking*, *waste bins*) in the reporting tool; and (iv) the option to attach photographs to reports; and the ability to flag accessible conditions in addition to barriers. Additional suggestions included map rotation, integration with municipal work-site monitoring systems, and voice command support. These findings were partially incorporated into subsequent development of the web application.

3. Results

This section presents the main outcomes of the Tracce project, combining the results of the spatial analysis of Monza's pedestrian network with the operational evidence collected through the Tracce.app platform. The findings illustrate how the integration of detailed geospatial data, accessibility-oriented network analysis, and participatory digital tools can support both the identification of structural accessibility barriers and the monitoring of their impacts on everyday mobility. The results are organized into two complementary components: first, the analytical outputs generated through the WebGIS interactive platform, aimed at supporting planning and decision-making processes; second, the usage data collected through the web application Tracce.app, providing insights into user behavior, accessibility needs, and perceived barriers within the urban environment.

3.1 WebGIS Analysis and Potential Use

Building on the mapped pedestrian graph and its associated attributes, a set of GIS analyses was developed to produce an objective, structured assessment of the state of Monza's pedestrian network, highlighting critical conditions, discontinuities, and priority intervention areas. The *Pedestrian Network Coverage Index* was calculated by constructing a simplified vehicular graph and applying a 10-metre lateral buffer to each road edge, within which the length of associated pedestrian infrastructure was computed. The resulting ratio indicates:

- Values ≥ 2 correspond to adequate pedestrian coverage (infrastructure on both sides);
- Values between 1 and 2 indicate partial coverage;
- Values below 1 indicate scarce or absent pedestrian infrastructure.

Results show that 47% of road edges fall in the adequate coverage class, 9% show partial but significant coverage, and approximately 42% are characterized by insufficient or absent pedestrian infrastructure, predominantly in peripheral areas with agricultural or industrial land use.

The *Intersection Crossing Completeness Index* quantified the number of pedestrian crossings at each intersection, drawing on 988 crossings surveyed across the municipality, associated with vehicular nodes via 10-metre buffers. Results reveal that only 10% of intersections present three crossings and 12% have four or more. By contrast, 18% of intersections have only two crossings, 26% have one, and approximately 33% have no pedestrian crossing at all, a significant structural deficiency of route continuity with direct implications for PRM safety and accessibility.

The *Pedestrian Network Completeness Index* compares 500-metre isometric analyses (approximately 5 walking minutes) computed on the accessible graph against the complete graph across a regular hexagonal grid of 601 cells. Approximately 30% of hexagons show index values between 0.9 and 1, indicating near-equivalence between accessible and complete graphs in central and consolidated urban areas, with exception of a limited number of critical areas, while index values decrease progressively with distance from the city center.

Figure 4 Pedestrian Network Completeness Index in the City of Monza.

The *Detour Analysis* was conducted on two complementary scales. At the local scale, a simulation of all origin-destination pairs crossing each intersection compared the length of the accessible pedestrian path (using only crossings equipped with ramps) with the straight-line distance, classifying intersections into three deviation categories: minimum, medium, and severe. Severe-deviation intersections represent locations where inadequate crossing provision forces users into substantial detours or, alternatively induces them to cross without appropriate infrastructure, increasing accident risk. At the systemic scale, a *Betweenness Centrality Analysis* was conducted on 31 million origin-destination relationships simulated within a 5-kilometre radius, using the same routing engine implemented in Tracce.app. The analysis was run on both the complete graph and the accessible graph, and their difference, the *Delta Betweenness Centrality*, identifies accessibility bottlenecks: segments that acquire disproportionate strategic importance under accessibility constraints, whose absence or degradation would substantially reduce accessible network connectivity. Quantitative results show that accessibility constraints induce an average route detour of approximately 533 meters, with approximately 10% of routes unaffected and over 44% subjected to detours exceeding 500 meters.

These analytical outputs were made accessible through an interactive WebGIS platform, available at <https://app.transformtransport.org/monza/pebaGIS.html> in both Italian and English format and addressed to public administrators, planners, researchers, and citizens. The platform's main interface is structured around an interactive map with a dynamic legend, contextual pop-ups, and statistical charts, organized across three distinct visualization modes. The *Network Mode* enables visualization of pedestrian network attributes such as sidewalk categories, ZTL roads, staircase segments, crossings, alongside quantitative indicators (i.e., *accident density, lighting, sidewalk width, slope*), with an interactive filtering mechanism allowing chart-to-map brushing. The *Intersections Mode* presents the detour analysis at each intersection with the three-level classification and displays the worst-case accessible route alongside its quantitative metrics. Finally, the *Network Analysis Mode* presents the three Betweenness Centrality layers (i.e. *complete network, accessible network, Delta BC*) and aggregates detour statistics, providing planners with a spatial evidence base for prioritizing PEBA investments.

Figure 5 Main interface of the WebGIS platform in Network Mode, available at: <https://app.transformtransport.org/monza/pebaGIS.html>

3.2 Web Application: Functionality and Usage Results

Tracce.app is a web application, browser-accessible without installation and viewable on the device home screen with native app-like behavior, designed to support accessible pedestrian route planning and participatory barrier reporting for PRM users in Monza. At first use, an onboarding screen presents terms of use, privacy policy, and consent options. Users then select one of four profiles, each pre-configured with routing parameter values consistent with typical profile needs. From the profile detail screen, users can access a parameter customization panel to adjust hard constraints (i.e., *ramp requirement at crossings, step avoidance, minimum sidewalk width*) and soft cost weights (i.e., *accident penalization, lighting preference, slope penalization*). For each origin-destination pair, the application simultaneously calculates and displays two route alternatives: the shortest path by distance, and the accessible path calculated with the multi-criteria cost function based on active profile. The interface provides a comparative panel showing the delta between the two options, the number of steps avoided, the number of crossings without ramps avoided, and the number of sub-minimum-width segments avoided, making route trade-offs transparent. Navigation mode tracks the user's real-time GPS position, updating orientation based on direction of travel. The reporting function allows users to geolocate and categorize accessibility issues in nine predefined categories (i.e., *uneven surface, missing ramp, insufficient width, illegal parking, excessive slope, missing crossing, waste/debris, tree/pole obstruction, other*), with optional free-text comment and contact details. Upon submission, a georeferenced record is transmitted to the backend, constituting a dynamic informational layer for continuous graph data quality improvement.

Figure 6 Tracce.app screens: Accessible POIs, route example, and final feedback message.

The application was officially launched on the 13th of February 2026 during a press conference at the Municipality of Monza, followed by a door-to-door leafleting campaign on the 26th of March 2026 and a public presentation on the 18th of April 2026 at a community event promoted by the Monza municipality. The monitoring phase covered the 13th of February to the 12th of June 2026. By the monitoring close date, 108 unique users had interacted with the platform, compared to the 86 at an intermediate extraction on the 14th of April 2026, and 259 valid route searches were analyzed, from which the system computed 480 routes. Of the 259 searches, 221 (85.3%) returned an accessible route, while 38 (14.7%) did not yield an accessible solution under the active profile constraints.

Profile	Description	Total OD	Accessible OD	No Accessible Solution
Wheelchair user	Most restrictive constraints	121 (46.7%)	90	31 (25.6%)
Parent with stroller	Intermediate constraints	45 (17.4%)	38	7 (15.6%)
Person with motor disability	Moderate constraints	27 (10.4%)	27	0 (0%)
Other	Least restrictive	66 (25.5%)	66	0 (0%)
Total		259	221 (85.3%)	38 (14.7%)

Table 2 Route search results by user profile (13 February - 12 June).

The wheelchair user profile accounted for the largest share of searches (121 out of 259, 46.7%) and simultaneously the highest proportion of searches without an accessible solution (31 out of 121, 25.6%), reflecting the strictness of constraints associated with this profile. Profiles with less restrictive constraints returned accessible solutions in all monitored cases, suggesting that the network is generally adequate for less constrained mobility needs while remaining significantly deficient for the most demanding accessibility requirements. Over the monitoring period, 41 barrier reports were submitted by 9 unique users. The most frequently reported category was uneven or degraded surfaces (22.0%), confirming that pavement maintenance constitutes a critical accessibility dimension independent of formal infrastructure provision. Missing crossings (12.2%) and insufficient sidewalk width (12.2%) followed, consistent with the structural deficiencies identified by

GIS analysis. Reports classified as ‘Other’ predominantly described entirely missing sidewalks, excessively sloped ramps, and malfunctioning traffic signals.

Spatially, reports showed a significant concentration in the San Giuseppe neighborhood (Via Andrea Lissoni, Via Angelo Ramazzotti, Via Monsignor Giuseppe Baraggia, Via Gaetano Donizetti, Via Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart), suggesting systemic rather than episodic infrastructure deficiencies consistent with the low *Pedestrian Network Completeness Index* values recorded for that area. Collectively, the usage results confirm the alignment between user-perceived barriers and the structural deficiencies identified through GIS analysis and participatory workshops, validating the multi-method approach adopted by the Tracce project.

Figure 7 Flowchart of all routes generated by users belonging to the “Wheelchair User” profile.

4. Conclusions and Future Works

The Tracce project has demonstrated the feasibility and value of an integrated approach to urban accessibility that combines participatory co-design, systematic GIS mapping, AI-assisted barrier detection, and digital tool development within a single, coherent research framework. By placing the lived experience of people with reduced mobility at the center of the research process, from the initial identification of priority barriers to the iterative testing and refinement of the web application, the project has produced a set of outputs that are both analytically rigorous and operationally actionable.

The GIS analyses carried on through the project have revealed a heterogeneous accessibility landscape: while central and consolidated urban areas of Monza present relatively adequate pedestrian infrastructure, substantial deficiencies affect the peripheral fabric of the city. The findings of this analytical process are varied and provide decision-makers with an objective, spatially explicit basis for prioritizing infrastructure investments within the PEBA. On the intersection infrastructure, it emerged that approximately 33% of intersections lack any pedestrian crossing, and that accessibility constraints induce an average route detour of 533 meters, with over 44% of route pairs affected by detours exceeding 500 meters. On the network, the *Delta Betweenness Centrality* analysis helped identifying specific bottleneck segments whose maintenance or improvement would yield disproportionate benefits for accessible network connectivity.

The Tracce web application constitutes a first operational prototype of an accessible routing system designed from the ground up through participatory methods: with 108 unique users, 259 route searches, and 41 georeferenced barrier reports in the first four months of deployment, the platform demonstrates the feasibility of combining personalized accessible navigation with crowdsourced data enrichment in a continuous feedback loop between user experience and infrastructure knowledge. The project has also shown the current potential and limitations of AI-assisted barrier detection, confirming AI as a promising complement to field surveys and GIS mapping for large-scale monitoring.

Looking forward, several development directions emerge from the project experience. The consolidation of continuous data update mechanisms is a primary priority: urban accessibility is a dynamic condition that varies with construction works, temporary obstacles, and maintenance cycles, and the structural integration of user reports and periodic AI-assisted reassessment into a data lifecycle will be necessary to maintain the relevance of the pedestrian graph over time. A second direction concerns the evolution of the routing system toward more adaptive, personalized models capable of progressively learning individual user preferences. A third involves the integration of Tracce with other municipal digital services, such as local public transport, roadworks monitoring, and accessibility databases for Points of Interest, in order to provide more comprehensive and dynamic information. Finally, the methodology and tools developed for Monza may be transferred and scaled to other municipalities, contributing to a replicable model for digital-enhanced PEBA processes. In conclusion, the Tracce project has shown how the convergence of participatory methods, open geospatial data, AI technologies, and digital tools can transform the PEBA from a static planning document into a continuous, adaptive process of monitoring and improving urban accessibility, a structural dimension of urban quality and sustainable mobility.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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The following Web links provide direct access to the main project documents:

- Website of the project: <https://transformtransport.org/research/inclusive-mobility/icts-in-support-of-monzas-peba-plan-for-eliminating-architectural-barriers/>
- Web GIS: <https://app.transformtransport.org/monza/peba.html>
- Web App: <https://tracce.app/>

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